

Crowding of Atlantic salmon in net-pen before slaughter

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Abstract

Crowding of Atlantic salmon in a net-pen before slaughter was studied from start to finish. Environmental parameters (dissolved oxygen, temperature, pH, current velocity and water depth), fish behaviour, ventilation rates, blood chemistry (cortisol, pH and lactate), initial pH in white muscle and related time to onset of rigor mortis were assessed to evaluate the condition of the fish during crowding. Even though the fish in the net-pen were severely stressed before the crowding operation started, crowding led to considerably higher cortisol levels and ventilation rates. However, prolonged crowding did not significantly increase the cortisol levels further. The initial pH of the muscle also showed that the fish were severely stressed before crowding, but in this case the fish were not further stressed to exhaustion by crowding. Using fish behaviour as single stress indicator for evaluation welfare-related issues must be done with caution since under the prevailing circumstances, diametrically opposed conclusions were drawn from monitoring fish behaviour versus evaluation of acute stress (blood chemistry and muscle biochemistry). The results were discussed in terms of animal welfare, stress, fish processing, and whether choice of technology actually could improve conditions for crowded fish in cases where they are slaughtered just after crowding.